

" THE TERROIN AS AN ELEMENT OF THE COMBAT SITUATION "

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Annotation: This article provides information on the terrain as an element of the combat situation

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Terrain is a part of the earth's surface. The totality of its irregularities is called relief, and all objects located on it, created by nature and human labor (rivers, forests, settlements, etc.), are local objects. Local objects occupying vast territories (inland seas, mountain systems, deserts, etc.) are commonly referred to as geographical objects.

Local objects on the basis of the uniformity of their economic and military significance are divided into groups called topographic elements of the terrain. The main topographic elements of the terrain are relief, hydrography, vegetation cover, soils, road network, settlements, industrial, agricultural and socio-cultural objects.

The topographic elements of the terrain are interconnected. Thus, the relief significantly affects the configuration of roads, the layout of settlements, the distribution of soils and vegetation; soils largely determine the nature of vegetation, the depth of groundwater.

In various combinations and in combination with the climate, topographic elements form a wide variety of terrain types. Each type of terrain has its own characteristics that have a positive or negative impact on various aspects of military operations of troops: operational formation (formation of combat formations) in the offensive and defense, the use of military equipment, the speed of the march and the pace of the offensive, the organization of the protection of troops from modern means of destruction.

Tactical properties of the terrain.

The properties of the terrain that influence the organization and conduct of hostilities, the use of weapons and equipment in combat, are called tactical properties. The main ones include terrain patency, its protective properties, conditions for orientation, observation, camouflage and firing. In some areas, the conditions of engineering equipment of the terrain and water supply have a significant impact on the conduct of hostilities.

Terrain patency is a property of the terrain that facilitates or hinders the movement of troops. It is determined primarily by the presence of paved roads. So, in a wooded, swampy, mountainous, desert area, highways acquire the importance of the most important directions along which the main efforts of the troops are concentrated.

Movement in battle is carried out where it is necessary according to the conditions of the situation and the terrain conditions allow. Therefore, determining the possibility of movement without roads of military and other equipment is of particular importance. Terrain patency without roads is greatly influenced by the nature of the terrain, soils and vegetation, the presence of natural and artificial obstacles (swamps, rivers, lakes, etc.).

When assessing terrain patency, tactical and technical characteristics of combat and other equipment, the time of year and weather conditions are always taken into account.

Protective properties of the terrain — the properties of the terrain that weaken the effect of damaging factors of nuclear and other weapons and facilitate the organization of the protection of troops. They are determined by the nature of the relief, vegetation cover, the presence of various natural and artificial shelters on the ground. Deep and winding terrain folds, woodlands and other shelters significantly reduce the degree of damage from a nuclear explosion.

The protective properties of the terrain are most fully manifested if they are used in combination with other measures, for example, the dispersal of forces, their camouflage and engineering equipment of the terrain. Skillful use of the protective properties of the terrain is one of the most important requirements for the organization of modern combat.

Orientation conditions are terrain properties that help determine your location and the desired direction of movement relative to the sides of the horizon, surrounding terrain objects, as well as relative to the location of your troops and enemy troops. They are determined by the presence on the ground of characteristic relief elements and local objects that clearly stand out among other objects in their appearance or position and are convenient for use as landmarks.

The ability of each unit leader to quickly and accurately navigate the terrain contributes to the correct formulation of combat tasks for units and firepower, accurate targeting and reliable management of units during combat.

Observation conditions are the properties of the terrain that contribute to obtaining information about the enemy, his forces and means. They are determined by the degree of visibility of the surrounding area, the viewing range and depend on the nature of the terrain, vegetation cover, settlements and other objects that hinder the view of the terrain, as well as meteorological conditions. The more ravines, gullies, heights, woody and shrubby vegetation, various kinds of buildings on the terrain, the less favorable the observation conditions are.

Proper organization of observation and the results obtained at the same time help the commander to comprehensively assess the situation and make an informed decision.

Camouflage terrain properties — terrain properties that allow you to hide the location and movement of troops from the enemy. They are determined by the presence of natural shelters formed by landforms, vegetation and settlements. The most favorable conditions

for the camouflage of troops are created on rough terrain. Gullies, gullies, ravines create good conditions for hiding troops in areas of concentration, and also serve as paths for covert maneuver and communication with the rear.

The camouflage properties of the terrain depend on the time of year, day and weather conditions. So, in summer, deciduous forests provide reliable camouflage of units not only from ground, but also from aerial surveillance. In winter, in such a forest, the equipment is easily visible against the background of snow cover.

The camouflage properties of the terrain make it possible to hide objects both from visual observation of the enemy and from his reconnaissance using various technical means, to ensure reliable concealment of the location of troops, to increase the surprise of striking the enemy.

The conditions of firing are the properties of the terrain that ensure the covert location of firepower, firing from guns and small arms at maximum ranges, as well as the correction of firing. They depend mainly on the nature of the relief and vegetation cover.

When determining the conditions for firing, they establish areas of terrain in the location of the enemy and their troops that are not shot through from small arms and PTS, choose advantageous positions for firing.

The conditions of the engineering equipment of the terrain depend on the type of soils, the water table, the availability of building materials, as well as on the nature of natural and artificial shelters and obstacles. The condition of soils largely determines the amount of work on the preparation of column tracks, the separation of trenches, trenches, the construction of shelters for personnel and equipment. The possibility of building various structures depends on the depth of groundwater. The presence of building materials on the ground (wood, crushed stone, gravel, sand, etc.) largely determines the scope and timing of engineering work.

Tactical classification of terrain

Tactically, the terrain is divided according to the conditions of patency, observation and camouflage, as well as the degree of roughness.

According to the conditions of passability, the terrain can be passable, impassable and impassable.

The passable terrain almost does not limit the speed, direction of movement of tracked vehicles and allows repeated movement on a false trail, although some places need to be bypassed or reinforced (equipped with passages). The movement of wheeled vehicles of ordinary patency is somewhat difficult. It is possible to use almost unhindered (except in certain directions) combat vehicles in various formations and the movement of columns. The passable terrain contributes to the most effective use of SMEs and SOon.

Impassable terrain is accessible to tracked vehicles, but at a lower speed than on passable terrain. Freedom of maneuver and movement of several cars on the same track are limited. The movement of wheeled vehicles of ordinary cross-country is almost impossible. Such terrain makes it difficult to use military equipment in deployed combat formations, the movement of columns is possible only on roads and specially equipped column tracks. The impassable terrain has a negative impact on the pace of the advance and offensive of troops, the maneuvering of forces and means along the front and from the depths.

The impassable terrain is inaccessible to the movement of tracked and wheeled vehicles without performing significant work on laying column tracks.

According to the conditions of observation and camouflage, the terrain is divided into open, semi-closed and closed.

The open area is a flat and slightly hilly treeless territory, up to 75% of the area of which is clearly visible in all directions from commanding heights.

This area is less favorable for protection from the damaging effects of conventional and nuclear weapons, has insufficient masking properties from ground and air surveillance. The lack of natural shelters makes it difficult to covertly concentrate troops and maneuver. The organization of defense in an open area is much more complicated.

Semi-closed terrain is transitional from open to closed. As a rule, in a semi-closed area, the area occupied by natural shelters is about 20%, about 50% of the area is visible from command heights. When units are located on the spot, their disguise is almost completely provided by natural masks.

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